

EuroGO-SHIP
Enhancing ocean observations

D3.4. Report on carbonate reference material production

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1. Introduction

The EuroGO-SHIP project aims to establish a European Research Infrastructure (RI) for hydrography, which is essential for understanding the ocean's role in climate, ecosystems, and human activities. However, the current hydrographic observation system in Europe is fragmented, inefficient, and insufficient to meet the growing demands of science and society. Therefore, there is a need for a coordinated, harmonized, and sustainable RI that can provide high-quality, reliable, and interoperable hydrographic data and related services to the European and global community.

The EuroGO-SHIP project has four main objectives:

- To develop a governance and business model for the European RI for ship-based hydrography;

- To design and implement shared facilities and services that can enhance the efficiency and quality of hydrographic and other ship-based observations;
- To demonstrate the principles and operations of the European RI for hydrography through pilot activities;
- To engage and network with relevant stakeholders and users of hydrographic data and related services.

This deliverable, D3.4 Report on carbonate system reference material production, reports on the production of secondary reference material (RM) for marine inorganic carbon observations. Using the metrological definition, the name secondary RM is misleading, and the correct term is in-house or working RM. The global marine inorganic carbon community associated to hydrography depends on measurements of discrete water samples for total dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC), total alkalinity (TA), and pH to characterize the inorganic carbon content of seawater in the ocean water column. The aim of these measurements reaches from ocean acidification experiments to observations of global trends of anthropogenic carbon in the deep sea. The quality of these kind of measurements increased immensely since the creation and adoption of standard operating procedures (SOPs) and the introduction of standard seawater that is calibrated for its DIC and TA content in the 1990s through the laboratory of Prof. Andrew Dickson at Scripps Institution of Oceanography (SIO; US) (e.g., Dickson, 2001). Currently, the oceanographic community uses misleading terminology referring to the standard seawater distributed by SIO as certified reference material (CRM) when the correct metrological term is RM. This issue is clarified by García-Ibáñez and Easley (2024):

“One reality is even though the materials are often referred to by the community as “CRMs”, based on practices defined within the field of metrology and based on the ISO definitions, these materials do not fit the current criteria for certified. They are indeed RMs proven to be stable and homogenous but with non-certified values. To qualify as CRMs, they would require a somewhat more rigorous value assignment process, including the developments of uncertainty budgets that incorporate all significant components of uncertainty. The materials are currently reported with measurement repeatability as the only source of uncertainty.”

An urgent issue, unsettling the global marine inorganic carbon community, regards the near future provision of those RM, which revealed to be weakly sustained during the COVID-19

pandemic and, therefore, uncertain in the future. In addition, the current supply of RMs from SIO is limited and costly, and there is a need for alternative producers of RMs. Therefore, efforts have been undertaken by the International Ocean Carbon Coordination Project (IOCCP) and the Global Ocean Acidification – Observation Network (GOA-ON) to secure the provision for CO₂-in-seawater RMs for the measurements on a broader international basis, including the idea of regional hubs, one of which is supposed to be in the European/African region.

1.1. Objectives and scope of the deliverable

The aim of this task is to produce and distribute a batch of in-house RM for marine inorganic carbon measurements for the European marine carbon community, following the procedures developed at SIO. Together with SIO's RMs, in-house RMs can be used to ensure the accuracy and comparability of DIC and TA measurements across different regions and time periods, as well as to calibrate and validate sensors and instruments. In addition to the classical approach of providing RM in borosilicate glass bottles, the aim of the deliverable was to investigate alternative storage solutions, like gas tight bags with higher volume (ca. 5 L). These alternative RM containers could be used for short campaigns (up to two months) like research cruises with high demands of RM. This activity was intended to demonstrate the feasibility and benefits of preparing and distributing in-house RMs at GEOMAR (Kiel, Germany), and to contribute to the global effort for establishing best practices for this process.

This task concentrated on the provision of RM for DIC and TA, as SIO does, since the laboratory at GEOMAR does not have adequate instruments for the determination of seawater pH yet.

1.2. Delays

The work towards this deliverable was delayed due to several reasons. However, the main task could be fulfilled (preparation of in-house RM), while the remaining tasks are underway (distribution of in-house RM). The reasons for delay were:

- The preparation of the in-house RM was taking place at the CO₂ laboratory at GEOMAR (Kiel, Germany) in May 2024. In 2023, the new building was finished for all departments of GEOMAR to be unified on the same campus, including the CO₂ laboratory. The actual date of moving was postponed several times, which caused the analytical work at the laboratory to stand still for several months. After the move in November 2023, it took longer than expected to get the instruments working in the

new laboratory as some of them got slightly damaged. The instruments are specialized instruments and the repairs needed to be accomplished by the GEOMAR lab technicians with the technical assistance of the manufacturer.

- In 2023, a postdoc was hired to assist with the preparation and evaluation of the in-house RM. After 3 months working in EuroGO-SHIP, she was offered a permanent position in a different institute and left the project.

However, the above-mentioned delays will be overcome by summer/autumn 2024. During the course of this update, in situ filtration and sterilization of seawater—assumed sterile (not tested)—were carried out for the preparation of substandards in the laboratory. In addition, initial test measurements were performed on substandards filled in plastic bags.

2. KPI Approach

This section provides an overview of how the activities and initiatives outlined in Task 3.2 on Pilot Activities align with the relevant Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) of the EuroGO-SHIP project. Progress against KPIs is regularly assessed and reported, ensuring transparency and accountability within the EuroGO-SHIP project. Within Task 3.2, the KPI associated to it is the following:

KPI-2.1 determined the requirement, cost and possible supply models for new user facilities including: ... b) Certified reference materials (CRMs) for nutrients and Reference Materials (RMs) for inorganic carbon;

As mentioned above, the work in Task 3.2 regarding the in-house RM for marine inorganic carbon measurements suffered several delays. However, one batch of in-house RM was prepared. This enabled us to describe the requirements that are needed for its preparation, including its value assignment.

3. Preparation

The preparation of the in-house RM batches is based on experience during a similar approach that was developed during the COVID-19 pandemic at GEOMAR together with the European Research Infrastructure “Integrated Carbon Observation System (ICOS)”. During this time, several online meetings took place between members of the laboratory of Andrew Dickson (SIO; US) and GEOMAR (Kiel, Germany) to discuss their procedures for preparing the batch of homogeneous water and filling bottles.

For the preparation of the batch, we used 1 m³ oceanic surface seawater collected from an oligotrophic area of the tropical Northeast Atlantic Ocean. It was not clear when and from where the water was taken as it was stored at GEOMAR for several years. For a second batch we filled another 1 m³ tank with surface water (from the Northeast Atlantic Ocean) using the ship’s fire hose. Of course, smaller volumes can be used. During the last three years, we performed several experiments with the seawater and found it to be stable with respect to the carbonate system for at least one year after it was bottled.

Both seawater batches were from oligotrophic parts of the ocean and weren’t treaded for potential impact of biomass. When collecting water from regions with higher biological productivity (e.g., coastal ocean), the organic load could be massive. One option would be to filter the sweater at the place of collection. To test the suitability of such an approach we present an option for seawater collection that includes filtering the water.

3.1. Seawater collection

To collect seawater from a coastal site (Boknis Eck in the Eckernförde Bay, Baltic Sea, Germany: 54°31.77’ N, 10°02.36’ E) for the preparation of the in-house RM batch, a filtration and sterilization system was set up onboard a vessel. The system consisted of three filter housings connected in series, each containing a polypropylene filter bag (Fuhr GmbH, Beutel-Element BP-420) with decreasing pore sizes of 25 µm, 5 µm, and 1 µm, respectively (Fig. 1A). These filters were connected via hoses, allowing seawater to sequentially pass through each stage of filtration. After the final filtration step, the water flowed (ca. 30 L min⁻¹) through a UV sterilization lamp (Purion 1000, Fig.1B), also connected by hoses, before entering an Intermediate Bulk Container (IBC) for storage (volume ca. 1000 L). The seawater was collected using a submersible pump (Lowara Scuba series, Fig.1C) with a valve in-between to regulate the flow rate (Fig. 1D). Once the tank is filled with seawater it is advisable to pump the water through the UV sterilisation for several hours. This setup ensured that seawater was pumped

efficiently from the ocean, through the filtration units and UV lamp, and finally into the IBC container under controlled conditions, producing clean, filtered, and sterilized seawater suitable for the use as a substandard in carbon system analyses.

Figure 1. A: Filter setup on IBC container for seawater collection. B: UV-lamp connected with filter housings. C: Connection of submersible (diving) pump with a hose to collect seawater. D: Flow-control valve connected by a hose (orange) to the submersible pump and by an additional hose (blue) to the filter housings.

The in-situ filtering and sterilisation was done in the south western Baltic Sea close to the Kiel bay in early summer 2025. The batch will be tested in the following months for stability.

3.2. Batch preparation

A subsample of a seawater batch of ca. 120 L was filled into a non-transparent tank (for the following we used sweater from the Atlantic Ocean). The seawater was then poisoned with a 24 mL of saturated mercuric chloride solution to prevent any biological activity and stored in a dark and temperature-controlled room. Three days before the seawater was filled into borosilicate glass bottles, a submersible pump was inserted to ensure turbulent mixing within the batch for homogenization of the CO₂ content. The seawater was pumped through a UV sterilization unit (Purion 1000) to ensure a sterile batch and improve long-term stability. To provide a constant atmosphere above the seawater, a pump providing clean atmospheric air at a flow rate of approximately 50 mL min⁻¹ (see Fig. 2) was connected. Alternatively, a gas bottle with a constant CO₂ content similar to atmospheric CO₂ can be connected.

In addition to the pump, a thermosalinograph (Seabird SBE37) was deployed in the tank to also measure salinity. This can also be done with discrete samples, if possible (Note: the seawater contains mercury chloride!).

Figure 2. Schematic of the batch preparation for seawater inorganic carbon in-house RM. TSG stands for thermosalinograph.

3.3. Bottling

To ensure the headspace is renewed faster than room air (even when removing seawater from the tank), the submersible pump was turned off and the flow rate of the headspace gas

is increased to ca. 100 mL min⁻¹ approximately one hour before bottling. Figure 3 shows a schematic of the setup used to bottle the batch. We used borosilicate glass bottles (250 mL and 500 mL) that were rinsed and tempered at 500°C for approximately 5 hours. A hose was introduced to the bottom of the tank, leading to a peristaltic pump, that was connected to a foot pedal to operate the pump.

Figure 3. Schematic of the sampling setup for bottling the batch. TSG stands for thermosalinograph

The free end of the hose was then introduced into a clean glass bottle and the bottle was filled from the bottom to the top, leaving approximately 1 % of the bottle volume as headspace (Dickson et al. 2007). The stopper was greased (using Apiezon®L) and the bottles were immediately closed as recommended in Dickson et al. (2007).

Use of wine bags as short-term storage

In addition, we also filled air-tight plastic bags (volume: 5 L) to test their suitability for short term stability (up to two months) of DIC and TA. The bags were regular plastic bags being used to store wine or juice (Fig. 4). In this approach, the valve of a plastic bag is first removed to allow access to the interior. A clean filling hose is then inserted carefully to the bottom of the bag, ensuring that RM will enter from the base upwards. Using the peristaltic pump, the bag is filled with RM. Once the plastic bag is completely filled, the valve is immediately reattached and secured to minimize the RM's exposure to atmospheric air. This method is being

evaluated as a flexible and potentially more practical alternative for certain field sampling applications, particularly where glass bottles are impractical due to space or fragility concerns.

Figure 4. Plastic bags that were filled for test purpose with in-house carbon reference water.

Bottling from plastic bags

There are two potential ways of using such plastic bags. Either the bags are connected to the measuring systems directly or they can be filled in glass bottles. We tested here the latter, which could be a suitable way during a cruise. One bag is enough water to fill at least 15 250 mL glass bottles. For the bottling of in-house RM from plastic bags, 250 mL borosilicate glass bottles with ground-glass stoppers are used. Prior to filling, each glass stopper is lightly greased with silicone grease to ensure an airtight seal and then placed upside down next to the corresponding bottle on a clean surface to avoid contamination. A clean, flexible hose is attached to the valve of the plastic bag, which contains the RM. The bag is positioned on its side to allow for gravity-driven flow. The free end of the hose is carefully inserted into the bottom corner of the 250 mL bottle, allowing RM to flow gently from the bottom upwards, displacing air while minimizing bubble formation. The bottle is filled until a small volume of RM overflows, ensuring that no air remains in the bottle. The hose is then removed out of the bottle, and the valve of the plastic bag is immediately closed to prevent any backflow or contamination. The bottles were filled leaving approximately 1 % of the bottle volume as headspace (Dickson et al. 2007). The greased glass stopper is then inserted firmly into the bottle, creating an airtight seal. Finally, the stopper is secured in place with an elastic band and a plastic clip to prevent gas exchange with the atmosphere during storage and transport.

3.4. Plastic bags first results

Initial test measurements on plastic bags were conducted within 2 months after filling. Test Measurement 1 focuses on the stability of the RM in plastic bags during individual fillings, i.e. how comparable are the bottles filled from the same bag. For all test measurements, two plastic bags were used and analyzed for changes in DIC and TA concentration during 2 weeks. In Test Measurement 1, plastic bag 01 showed an average DIC concentration of $2071.36 \mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$ (± 1.08), while plastic bag 02 showed $2079.65 \mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$ (± 1.11) (Fig. 5 a). The TA values ($\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$) had average concentrations of 2213.64 (± 0.53) for plastic bag 01 and 2217.74 (± 0.96) for plastic bag 02 (Fig. 9 b). Although the plastic bags differed from each other in terms of the absolute DIC and TA concentrations, each bag individually showed stable values with a difference of approximately $3 \mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$ between measuring day 1 and 7 (plastic bag 01) and 7 and 8 (plastic bag 02) for DIC respectively $3 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ at day 13 (plastic bag 02) for TA. From the setup here it could not be determined if the difference between the first and the last sample was due to instrument drift or due to the order of filling.

Figure 5. Testmeasurement 1: Stability of the RM in plastic bags over time. (a) DIC concentrations ($\mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$) in plastic bag 01 (blue) and plastic bag 02 (orange) measured over a period of thirteen days with mean values of 2071.36 (plastic bag 01) and 2071.36 (plastic bag 02). (b) TA concentrations ($\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$) in plastic bag 01 (blue) and plastic bag 02 (orange) measured on days 7 and 13 with mean values of 2213.64 (plastic bag 01) and 2217.74 (plastic bag 02). Solid green lines represent the respective mean values; dashed red lines indicate \pm standard deviation (SD). The time represents the time in days after the RM was transferred from the plastic bag into the bottles.

Test Measurement 2 focused on the stability of the reference materials (RMs) with respect to bottling order in 250 mL borosilicate bottles. Again, two plastic bags were compared and analyzed for changes in DIC and TA concentrations. In Test Measurement 2, plastic bag 03 had an average DIC concentration of $2089.58 \mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$ (± 1.55), while plastic bag 04 had an average of $2081.54 \mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$ (± 1.79) (Fig. 6a). The TA values ($\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$) showed average concentrations of 2218.24 (± 1.12) for plastic bag 03 (Fig. 6b) and 2218.73 (± 1.62) for plastic bag 04 (Fig. 6c). The two plastic bags differed in DIC by approximately $8 \mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$, but showed stable values across the bottling order, with a maximum difference of about $6 \mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$ between bottling 4 and 8 (plastic bag 03) and bottling 3 and 4 (plastic bag 04) (Fig. 6a). Regarding TA, both plastic bags showed very similar mean values differed by approximately $0.5 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$, and they were stable across the bottling order, with a maximum difference of about $6 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ between bottling 5 and 10 (plastic bag 04) (Fig. 6c).

Figure 6. Stability of the RM with respect to bottling order in 250 mL borosilicate bottles across ten sequential bottlings. (a) DIC concentrations ($\mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$) in plastic bag 03 (blue) and plastic bag 04 (orange) with mean values of 2089.58 (plastic bag 03) and 2081.54 (plastic bag 04). (b) TA concentrations ($\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$) in plastic bag 03 with mean values of 2218.24. (c) TA concentrations ($\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$) in plastic bag 04 with mean values of 2218.73. The green lines represent the mean values, and the red dashed lines indicate \pm standard deviation (SD).

The current results using plastic bags as an alternative or additional filling method for reference material (RM) appear promising. Although only initial test measurements have been conducted, there is potential to improve both the filling of RM into the plastic bags and the subsequent bottling process from the bags into bottles. The results suggest that the used bags are suitable for storage of RM for several weeks. The difference in DIC values between the bags could be due to the filling procedure of the bags since no care was taken to prevent gas exchange during this process. Three of the four bags tested show TA values very close together (within 1 mol kg^{-1}). The tests with this kind of bags will continue to develop reliable methods for filling the bags and use them in the field.

The next steps would include:

- Using an alternative valve for the plastic bags to prevent gas exchange during filling and make it easier to fill them later into separate bottles.
- Testing the filling of plastic bags using a pump, and evaluating whether this method reduces differences in DIC and TA concentrations between individual bags
- Developing a setup for precise bottling of RM from the plastic bags and testing whether this reduces variability in DIC and TA concentrations between individual bottles

4. Value assignment

The filled bottles are stored in a dark place at room temperature (ca. 20°C). At least eight samples will be analysed for DIC and TA. These samples should be randomly picked from all bottles. At GEOMAR, we use a SOMMA system with a coulometer for DIC determination (Johnson et al., 1998) and a VINDTA system for TA determination (Mintrop et al., 2000). The instruments are calibrated using carbonate standards and the results will be quality-controlled using RMs from SIO. The values of these bottles should agree within $2 \text{ } \mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$ for both DIC and TA for them to be suitable to be used as in-house RMs. In case the agreement is worse, the batch is considered to be not stable.

The so produced RM will be measured in regular intervals (at least once per month) against RM from SIO to ensure stability with respect to DIC and TA. During the last three years, in previous projects using the same 1 m^3 water tank and procedures to produce in-house RM, it was found to be stable. Thus, we envisage the same success in RM stability.

5. Distribution and cost analysis

The in-house RM is to be distributed to members of the EuroGO-SHIP consortium. Yet, there are no alternative solutions for borosilicate bottles, and shipping glass bottles is quite cost extensive. One reason is the weight of the shipment (a bottle itself represents approximately 60 % of the RM weight) and another reason is the price and availability of these bottles, so that the empty bottles need to be shipped back. For a project like EuroGO-SHIP this might not be a huge issue, but projecting in the future the shipping also adds a logistical and organisational issue. It is a time-consuming process to organize shipping (packing, generate paperwork for shipping and customs clearance) and to keep a stable and suitable bottle inventory.

*Table 1: Breakdown of steps that add to the total cost of the preparation of in-house RM. **Please note:** The shown costs are only rough estimates and are shown for demonstration. They can vary substantially from lab to lab. Here we assume that one batch will produce 200 bottles (250 – 500 mL each).*

Step	Description	Estimated price per bottle
Seawater	The cost for accessing seawater can vary. A good solution is an opportunistic approach taking advantage of planned research cruises. Seawater can be filled in a container that can be delivered to the laboratory on land.	0 – 10 €
Filtration/Sterilisation/Homogenization	Depending on the origin of the seawater, it needs to be filtered and sterilized to ensure stability. The laboratory needs to provide the infrastructure (space, UV system, pump, etc.).	1 €
Bottle logistics	Borosilicate bottles need to be purchased and cleaned. The laboratory needs to provide the infrastructure (space, furnace, etc.).	12 €

Bottling	The batch needs to be bottled. Trained personnel and adequate equipment are needed to achieve a stable batch.	5 €
Value assignment	The laboratory needs to have equipment and expertise to achieve reliable analyses from the bottles. At least eight bottles should be used for value assignment and at least 10 bottles within 12 months should be analysed to guarantee a stable batch.	2 €
Distribution	The distribution includes packaging, logistics, and (customs) paperwork. This can be a time-consuming job depending how widely the material is distributed.	1 – 30 €
Sum		21 – 60 €

Table 1 breaks down the positions that add to the costs of RM. It is important to note that most steps are independent from the aimed quality of the RM. The analysis for value assignment is one of the lowest contribution amounts in the costs' break down, as we assume that the laboratory already exists for a scientific scope and the production of in-house RM is not the main task (therefore salary and depreciation is not accounted for). The bottle logistics and distribution are the biggest contributors. Finding alternative sample containers could reduce the cost estimate substantially. However, the cost estimates can not only vary between labs but also depending on the purpose. If the RM is only produced for in-house use the distribution position does not apply.

Cost–Benefit Analysis of Using Plastic Bags for RM Distribution during Research Cruises

As an alternative to glass bottles, the plastic bags offer cost-effective solution for RM handling and distribution, particularly in the context of research cruises. For example, during a typical cruise, it is common practice to analyze four RM bottles per day. Over a 28 day long cruise, this adds up to a total of 112 RM bottles.

By contrast, using plastic bags—each of which holds the equivalent of approximately ten bottles—could drastically reduce the number of containers required. With 4 RM per day, only

six plastic bags would be needed for the entire cruise. In this scenario, instead of bringing 112 glass bottles on board, one could bring 6 filled plastic bags and 10 to 20 reusable borosilicate bottles. They could be rinsed and refilled on board as needed, significantly reducing both transport volume and bottle-related costs.

The cost difference is substantial: 10 plastic bags cost approximately €21 in total, while 10 borosilicate bottles (250 mL with glass stoppers) cost around €450. Additionally, shipping costs for plastic bags are considerably lower due to their lighter weight and lower fragility. Thus, using plastic bags not only reduces financial and logistical burdens but also offers flexibility and space efficiency on board—factors that are especially valuable in long-duration or resource-limited expeditions.

6. Conclusion and Outlook

The group at GEOMAR already prepared three batches of in-house RM but improved certain steps for the application during the EuroGO-SHIP project.

Using the method described above, a stable batch of seawater in-house RM for inorganic carbon measurements can be prepared. One prerequisite is the availability of clean (preferably oligotrophic) seawater to increase stability. However, with the described in-situ filtering and sterilisation, also water with higher biological activity might be used. Planned cruises should be used to sample big quantities (1 m³) of seawater with low biological content. This samples should be stored and observed for at least a year to ensure that there is no significant biological activity. There is a strong need for bigger containers with shorter storing times to be used during research cruises and the tested wine bags could be a solution to store RM for several weeks.

The provision of in-house RM can reduce the costs for quality assurance of DIC and TA measurements. However, the production of such a batch depends on a well-equipped laboratory and the distribution of such material can be a time-consuming job, that cannot be handled by existing marine inorganic carbon laboratories in addition to their research activities. In the future, we need a model to share these costs between several users. In addition, the community needs to have one provider of metrological CRMs to ensure high quality data of oceanic carbon measurements.

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